

A.C. Polarographic Studies on the Nature of the Capacity Peaks Observed with Organic Compounds at the Dropping Mercury Electrode. Part III. Effect of Medium

S. L. Gupta and S. K. Sharma

The effect of medium on the peak potentials and magnitudes of tensammetric and reduction peaks, observed with a number of organic compounds by a.c. polarography, has been studied. The fact that tensammetric peaks are practically absent or considerably reduced in magnitude and reduction peaks are considerably enhanced in non-aqueous medium has been utilised in determining the nature of the a.c. peaks observed with ionic and non-ionic organic compounds at the d.m.e. It has been confirmed that benzaldehyde exhibits a reduction peak in acidic medium, but in neutral or alkaline medium only tensammetric peak is obtained. Causes for the absence of adsorption as well as enhancement of the reduction peaks in non-aqueous media have also been discussed.

Breyer¹ has distinguished between a.c. polarography of organic compounds and tensammetry in aqueous medium by showing that tensammetric peaks are the outcome of the adsorption and desorption processes occurring at the dropping electrode, whereas a.c. polarographic reduction peaks of organic compounds are due to two processes, viz., electron transfer and adsorption-desorption phenomena, occurring simultaneously at the electrode. He termed such peaks as "composite peaks". Recently Gupta *et al.*² have shown how the composite nature of such peaks could be eliminated and distinguished from tensammetric peak by changing the medium from water to methanol.

The present investigation relates to the effect of a few non-aqueous solvents on the magnitude and peak potential of capacity peaks observed with a number of organic compounds, which are ionic and non-ionic in nature and are known to provide either tensammetric or reduction peak in aqueous medium.

EXPERIMENTAL

Bromothymol blue was of B.D.H. indicator quality. Other organic solid compounds used, except camphor, were either of B.D.H. or Merck and were recrystallised before use. Organic liquid substances were also pure samples of either Merck or B.D.H. and were redistilled in an all-glass fractionating column and the middle one-thirds of the distillates were used for experiments. Lithium chloride and sodium perchlorate were purified

1. *Austri. J. Sci.*, 1953, 16, 109.

2. *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1964, 7, 81.

by recrystallising May and Baker reagents. Mercury used for the dropping electrode was purified as mentioned in the previous communication³.

The experimental set up and the technique of measurement are the same as detailed in Part II of this series⁵ except that an a.c. ripple of 20mv (r.m.s.) was used. 0.1*M*-LiCl and 0.1*M*-NaClO₄ solutions in conductivity water and in pure organic solvents were used as aqueous and non-aqueous supporting electrolytes. Negative d.c. potentials were applied to the d.m.e. with respect to the S.C.E. Pure nitrogen was used to deaerate solutions and the experiments were carried out at a constant temperature of 20°±0.5° and at pH 6.8. The constants of the d.m.e. were $m=4.564$ mg./sec. and $t=1.8$ sec. per drop in 0.1*M*-KCl, open circuit. The results obtained are graphically represented in Fig. 1.

FIG. 1. Effect of the medium on the tensammetric peak as well as reduction peak in air-free solutions.

1. 1.0% *n*-amyl alcohol in aq. medium.
2. " " " in MeOH "
3. $4 \times 10^{-4}M$ nitroaniline in aq. "
4. $4 \times 10^{-4}M$ " in MeOH "

DISCUSSION

From Fig. 1 it appears that *n*-amyl alcohol shows considerable adsorption as well as desorption peak in aqueous medium, there being practically no adsorption or desorption peak in methanolic medium. Similarly with *p*-nitroaniline, adsorption as well as a reduction peak appears in aqueous medium; there is, however, practically no adsorption but a considerably enhanced reduction peak in methanolic medium. These observations are further supported by the data in Table I.

TABLE I

Substances.	Conc.	Aqueous medium.		Methanolic medium.	
		Peak potential.	Peak magnitude (% a.c.).	Peak potential.	Peak magnitude (% a.c.).
Tensammetric peaks.					
Bromothymol blue	0.004%	0.90 V	158.0 μ A	0.7 V	22.5 μ A
Cetyl pyridinium bromide	0.100	1.24	97.2	1.3 to 1.4	18.0 (rounded)
<i>o</i> -Cresol	1.600	1.33	132.0	0.4 to 0.7	27.2 (,,)
Resorcinol	1.200	1.30	73.3	0.5 to 0.6	19.8 (,,)
Phloroglucinol	1.200	1.00	120.0	0.6	27.1
<i>n</i> -Amyl alcohol	1.000	1.26	134.0	..	No peak
Benzoic acid	0.010M	1.06	79.0	1.2	5.0
*Aniline	0.100M	1.30	125.6	0.3 to 0.4	21.0 (rounded)
*Anisole	Satd.	1.35	222.6	1.1 to 1.2	18.7 (,,)
*Benzene	Satd.	1.00	142.1	1.0	7.1
Pyridine	1.00	1.55	220.0	0.3	14.2
Camphor	0.08	1.40	123.2	1.0	5.5
Benzaldehyde (pH 6.8)	2×10^{-3}	1.51	112.3	1.4 to 1.5	7.0
Reduction peaks.					
Nitrobenzene	$4 \times 10^{-4}M$	0.74	141.2	0.80	430.4
<i>p</i> -Nitroaniline	..	0.86	75.4	1.00	373.3
<i>o</i> -Nitrophenol	..	0.79	71.0	0.80	324.3
<i>p</i> -Nitrobenzoic acid	..	0.75	129.4	1.00	421.3
		1.30	20.3	1.40	250.0
3,5-Dinitrobenzoic acid	..	0.74	160.0	0.90	430.0
Methylene blue	0.08%	0.40	125.3	1.50	188.0
		1.54	99.5	1.30	53.3
Benzaldehyde (pH 4.6)	$2 \times 10^{-3}M$	1.26	128.8	1.50	118.0

* Satd. in aqueous medium & 4% in methanolic medium.

From Table I it appears that with organic compounds producing tensammetric peaks in aqueous medium, there is practically no adsorption and the desorption peaks are considerably decreased in magnitude, become rounded, and in some cases even completely disappear in methanolic medium. With organic compounds providing reduction peaks in methanolic medium, however, there is practically no adsorption, but considerably enhanced reduction peaks are obtained in all the cases studied except with benzaldehyde at pH 4.6

and with the second reduction peak of methylene blue, where the magnitude of the reduction peaks decreases in methanolic medium as compared to that in aqueous medium. This is ascribed mainly to the adsorption-desorption phenomenon associated to a large extent with these two composite peaks in aqueous medium, which is evident from their considerable extent of adsorption in the same medium. This aspect, however, needs further investigation.

It may also be stated, that benzaldehyde shows discrepancy from this behaviour, which is known to exhibit reduction wave in conventional polarography. Table I also shows that benzaldehyde provides a reduction peak in acidic medium, but in neutral and alkaline media only tensammetric peak is obtained. This observation also confirms the earlier views³⁻⁴ regarding the peak of benzaldehyde in alkaline medium.

Table II shows the effect of various organic solvents on 0.004% bromothymol blue as representative of tensammetric peak and 4×10^{-4} nitrobenzene as representative of reduction peak in aqueous medium. Here also it can be seen that the effect of various organic solvents on both types of peaks is the same as in case of methanolic medium.

TABLE II

Solvent.	Tensammetric peak*.		Reduction peak**.	
	Peak potential.	Peak magnitude (%a.c.).	Peak potential.	Peak magnitude (%a.c.).
	0.004% Bromothymol blue.		$4 \times 10^{-4}M$ Nitrobenzene.	
Methanol	0.7 v	22.5 μA	0.89 v	430.4 μA
Ethanol	0.7	17.1	0.94	203.3
Isopropanol	0.6 to 0.7	31.0 (rounded)	0.88	168.0
Pyridine	0.9	20.2	0.90	187.4
Acetone†	0.6 to 0.7	16.1 (rounded)	0.90	781.1
Methyl ethyl ketone‡	0.7	13.2	1.00	600.0

*Peak potential in aqueous media = 0.96V.

Peak magnitude in aqueous media = 158% a.c. (μA).

**Peak potential in aqueous media = 0.74v.

Peak magnitude in aqueous media = 141.2% a.c. (μA).

†Supporting electrolyte = 0.1M-NaClO₄.

It can also be seen in general that the peak potentials of organic compounds providing reduction peaks shift to more negative values when aqueous medium is changed to non-aqueous, whereas in the case of tensammetric peaks, the shift is to less negative potentials under similar conditions.

The fact that tensammetric peaks are practically absent or considerably reduced in magnitude and reduction peaks are considerably enhanced in non-aqueous medium can be utilised in determining the nature of the a.c. peaks observed with organic compounds at the d.m.e. Further, the nature of the a.c. peaks, particularly observed with organic compounds of ionic type, can also be determined by the use of non-aqueous medium, which is not possible from the studies of the change of pH of the buffer solution⁴.

Considerable adsorption in aqueous medium and practically no adsorption in non-aqueous medium may be ascribed to the larger effect of surface tension changes in aqueous medium and smaller effect in non-aqueous medium, respectively. The base currents are considerably reduced in non-aqueous media and hence a. c. reduction peaks of organic compounds in such media are more sensitive than those in aqueous medium.

Thanks are due to the authorities of the Birla College for the facilities and to C. S. I. R., New Delhi, for the award of a junior research fellowship to one of them (S.K.S.).

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
BIRLA COLLEGE,
PILANI, RAJASTHAN.

Received May 15, 1964.